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FINAL REPORT

DISCOVERY PROJECTS

Sloane Lab: Looking Back to Build Future Shared Collections

January 2025

University College London | The British Museum | Natural History Museum

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Executive Summary

The *Sloane Lab: looking back to build future shared collections* project set out to explore, along with four other Discovery Projects funded by the AHRC's Towards a National Collection programme, how cultural heritage, and the material that describes it, may be interconnected with digital platforms. The project focused on the challenges in bringing digitally together different types of collections across different organisations in ways that potential future users would find usable. The project deliberately sought to bring together natural history collections, books, manuscripts and objects catalogued in different ways on different digital platforms in different institutions. Centring participatory practice, the project worked to understand how different people from different backgrounds, levels of specialist knowledge and interests might want to learn from bringing these collections together, and how to build links across these digital collections in ways that supported rather than hindered their use.

More specifically, the Sloane Lab sought to explore such issues through the microcosm of the collection that was brought together by Sir Hans Sloane through a vast global network of traders, donors and enslaved individuals from the 1680s onwards. What made Sloane's collections an important and complex case study is that today it is dispersed across multiple national institutions, including the British Museum (BM), Natural History Museum (NHM) and British Library (BL). It is also made up of very different types of material, including prints, natural history and geology specimens, medicinal substances, books, objects etc. These have been subsequently catalogued, organised and described in very different ways. The organisations that now hold the dispersed collection use different digital catalogues that contain information about these collections. There has also been a long history of study of this collection and a desire to bring the collection back together digitally to support ongoing and future research that has taken on new urgency as the legacies of transatlantic enslavement, empire, and colonialism must be directly addressed by collection-based institutions.

The collection that Sloane brought together is of remarkable significance. By studying this collection, we can learn more about, for example, environmental history, including climate change and species distribution, and to learn more about what heritage objects mean to individuals and communities, how they may use them to learn more about their past and make sense of new futures. It is also a complicated and problematic collection. Sloane was able to finance his collecting practice over time through means that included his gains from transatlantic slavery, including investments in private companies such as the Royal African Company, and profits from plantations in Jamaica, originally inherited by his wife Elizabeth Rose and worked by the forced labour of enslaved people. Other income sources included the substantial sums he earned as a society and royal physician, rent collected on land he owned in London, and salaries from public offices. Nevertheless, for all the complexity, problematic nature and value of this collection, until the Sloane Lab project, it proved difficult to research with digital methods. The collection is held in more than three institutions and catalogued in more than five different digital systems, which each reflected the requirements of the institutions, curatorial and disciplinary expertise that shaped these systems. Accordingly, Sloane Lab sought to reaggregate this dispersed collection in a unified, digital information system.

This report summarises the research and findings of Sloane Lab, which has enabled substantial sections of the collections of Sir Hans Sloane to be researched in the aggregate with digital approaches for the first time. Set out in greater detail in the full report, the findings of the project are technical; participatory;

infrastructural; discipline-enriching; speak to future research on legacies of transatlantic enslavement, empire, and colonialism and digital cultural heritage; collections-based; and practical in nature. For ease of discussion, these strands of the project are set out separately, yet, as will be seen, all aspects of the project entailed sustained inter- and transdisciplinary engagement.

The main **technical output** of the project is the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base, which holds all data that has been collected, organised and unified by the Sloane Lab; data that has been gathered and mobilised from historical catalogues, contemporary records and other data sources. Through a rich portal that provides numerous interactive controls, the Knowledge Base offers end-users the ability to search, browse, conduct advanced search and produce data visualisations concerning (amongst others), people, places, objects and relationships. Moreover, the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base makes possible the crosslinking of Sloane's historical manuscript catalogue entries with contemporary database records found in museum collections today, therefore reconnecting the past and the present. Moreover, as set out below, the project has made numerous historical and present-day data sets that describe aspects of Sloane's collection available to all, in machine-readable formats, for the first time. This has had, among others, discipline-enriching benefits; for example, the project's extensive engagement with botanical data (Ray's *Historia Plantarum*; plant specimens in Sloane's Herbarium; Sloane's vegetable substances) has facilitated a new quality of access to this data. The result of this work is the publishing of data (in the Knowledge Base and on the corresponding NHM repository) that permit, for the first time, digital access to the taxonomic index of Sloane's Herbarium, allowing anyone to undertake a taxonomic search using Sloane's taxonomy. As such, the Sloane Lab shows how digital tools can be used to capture, mobilise, enrich and make historical collection interrogable, findings that are relevant to the cultural heritage sector and collections as data sectors. For all this, it also shows that substantial human labour is necessary at crucial points of even highly automated digital workflows, from data checking and cleaning to the transcription of fonts or handwriting that still cannot be fully automated by machines. These necessary human interventions are crucial, and digital workflows such as developed by Sloane Lab, cannot function without them.

The **participatory work** of the project started from an acknowledgement of the highly problematic aspects of the collection Sloane assembled; it was undertaken as a careful and intentional part of the project. Our aim was to understand what a broad range of interested and expert communities wanted, some of whom have connections to the source communities from whom objects and knowledge were extracted by Sloane and associates. By reaching out to a wide variety of interested and expert communities, we sought to understand the questions that communities wish to ask of a national collection and to respond to this in our technical work. Along with the co-creation of this knowledge, we devised instruments and protocols for working with diverse communities, which can be used by other heritage institutions and researchers across the UK and internationally, to work with communities to transform knowledge about unified collections. Moreover, we have generated new knowledge about what barriers currently exist for heritage organisations in the UK, Europe and Australia to be able to participate in this digital infrastructure.

A crucial part of this work was our Community Fellows programme. The Fellowship scheme brought new voices and expertise into the Sloane Lab. The eleven fellows undertook creative, critical and practice and/or research-led projects with the Sloane Lab's Knowledge Base and data, highlighting the opportunities for analysis and interpretation unlocked by the project. The diverse Fellowship projects ranged from artistic responses to Sloane data and material related to the colonial entanglements of the collection, to data visualisation, multivocality, absence, decentralised archival systems, Black life in the Sloane collections, and women in Sloane's 'Paper Museum'. We had the aspiration, considering the history of the collection, that at

least 50% of the fellowships should be awarded to Global Majority populations. Five of the eleven fellowships were ultimately taken up by members of Global Majority populations. As such, the Sloane Lab has demonstrated that the sustained engagement of communities of practice and interest can transform knowledge about digital heritage technologies, resulting in new ways to support individuals and diverse communities of interest to search, use, visualise and transform museum records and historical collections.

The **collections-based research** of the project was co-created in collaboration with UK partner museums and their local communities. The British Museum and Sloane Lab Touring Exhibition '*For the Curious and the Interested*' visited two venues – Down County Museum, Downpatrick (Northern Ireland) and Ceredigion Museum, Aberystwyth (Wales) between January and September 2024. The exhibition concept and title evoke Sloane's original intended audience for this collection when it came to the British Museum in 1753, and question what it means to be curious about collections in the 21st century. The exhibition concept was developed to encourage museum partners to explore themes around global collecting practices in the 17th and 18th centuries. Through the microcosm of 25 objects selected for exhibition from across the BM, NHM and BL collections, communities local to Wales and County Down were invited to engage with the histories and legacies of the collection in new ways. Confronting the complex history behind Sloane's vast collection, which was financed in part by profits from the transatlantic trade in enslaved people, the touring exhibition revealed how and why objects from across the world were brought together. It also explored some of the hidden stories of those Sloane worked with and relied upon for their knowledge and skills, including Indigenous and enslaved people, and other collectors, explorers and naturalists around the world. In this way, the exhibition formed a bridge between physical collections and data-driven research, exemplifying in the exhibition space the types of stories and connections that it is possible to make via the Sloane Lab digital portal.

Within organisations, Sloane Lab has had clear implications for the future work of the British Museum, Natural History Museum and other partners as they develop their own long-term strategies for their digital collections. For the BM and NHM, the project has enabled new work on one of the founding collections of the BM (and de facto founding collection of the NHM) to be continued, and on a scale not otherwise possible without the Towards a National Collection (TaNC) programme. The generation of new data and integration of data permits new ways of querying the collection and the analysis of the data provides new insights. These insights include how digital methods may help us to better understand the legacies of transatlantic enslavement, empire, and colonialism, and how they are as present in digital cultural heritage data as in the physical museum itself. For example, work on Sloane's botanical collections has allowed a precise estimate of its scale for the first time (130,308 specimens), revealed the extent and patterns of heterogeneity of the collection and of the data associated with it, and demonstrated unequivocally the close correlation between patterns of collecting and trade and colonial endeavours of the period, including the trade in enslaved people. Critically re-examining the BM's history and the history of the collection has and is a key priority for the organisation. The focus on how to work with different people from outside the museum world, and the clear focus of directly addressing challenging histories have been of great value to how colleagues at the BM think about and through these issues work with the collection. Sloane Lab also challenges the BM to work out how best to support and structure the people and the digital infrastructure needed to support the future of digital collections envisaged by TaNC. As such, the Sloane Lab collections-based research has resulted in new paradigms for heritage organisations who work with challenging collections, opening new conversations and partnerships that explore questions about who gets to rethink, to contribute to and shape collections and exhibitions, to reach across institutional boundaries, subject-specialities and even countries to better engage varied audiences and partnerships.

Considering these achievements and findings in the aggregate, Sloane Lab has not only opened unprecedented digital access to substantial sections of the previously siloed Sloane collection and the information that describes it. It has also demonstrated that diverse communities of interested and expert people must remain at the centre of ongoing work to imagine how digital platforms may be harnessed to tell new stories about what can be rediscovered, and reimagined, by linking collections.

Abstract

The founding collection of the British Museum is a rich and complex resource to explore how we can reconnect dispersed heritage collections using state of the art technologies. This is because the British Museum's original 1753 founding collection of Sir Hans Sloane is now split across three different institutions (the British Museum (BM), Natural History Museum (NHM) and the British Library (BL)) and the digital information that describes this founding collection sits in the different institutions in a range of different systems that are not currently set up to talk to one another. By focusing on catalogue records, and the vast, remaining collections of Sir Hans Sloane, the Sloane Lab project worked with interested communities and heritage organisations to link the present with the past to allow the currently broken links between Sloane's collections and catalogues to be re-established across the NHM, BL, BM (plus others that have relevant material). The main outcome of our project is the freely available, Sloane Lab Knowledge Base, which provides researchers, curators and the interested public with new opportunities to search, explore, and critically and creatively use and reuse digital cultural heritage.

Aims and Objectives

The Sloane Lab sought:

- To devise automated and augmented ways that are relevant to bringing together other collections in museums, galleries, libraries, and archives, of mending the broken links between the past and present of the UK's founding collection in the catalogues of the British Museum, Natural History Museum, and the British Library. For this, we used the collection of Sir Hans Sloane (1660-1753) as a microcosm through which to explore the technical, infrastructural, conceptual, historical, and social challenges faced in bringing together digital cultural heritage collections to help audiences use, learn and benefit from them.
- To deliver the public-facing, open access Sloane Lab of content, tools, and applications, opening new ways for national digital collections to be researched, explored, interlinked, and creatively engaged with.
- To facilitate richer, more critical understandings of the origins and development of museum collections by devising computational and conceptual approaches to detecting and exposing often-hidden processes like colonialism, empire and slavery that have shaped collections and their classifications. Sloane's collection was created through the economic, political, and cultural processes of Britain's increasing global entanglements of the 17/18th century, to which the infrastructure for a 21st-century national collection must respond.
- To evaluate the role of AI, Digital Humanities, Data Science, and historical collection records in the infrastructure of the future national collection, disseminating our findings globally as open source and reusable demonstrators and best practice documentation.
- To engage in ongoing, participatory research with diverse audiences, project partners, and the wider heritage sector to elaborate a digital cultural heritage participatory research paradigm and methodology that accommodates a plurality of perspectives and voices and does not limit the public to interacting with the national collection as curators, librarians, archivists, computer scientists and others have modelled it in existing platforms.
- To work with heritage institutions to identify factors like resources or investments that constrain an organisation's ability to contribute to national collection infrastructures and content and deliver policy recommendations for future digital heritage capacity and infrastructure investment.

As set out in detail in the following text, the project successfully achieved all its stated aims and objectives through the elaboration and making available of the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base; through extensive work with a wide community of diverse people interested in the Sloane collection; through participatory workshops, instruments such as questionnaires and traveling exhibitions; through the publication of research findings and new datasets and digital workflows; and through the numerous activities that Sloane Lab facilitated and participated in, in the UK and internationally, fostering new conversations about the history of the national collection and resulting, for example, in a new Sloane Lab display in the Enlightenment Gallery (Room 1) of the British Museum.

Partnership Structure

Collaborators

The Sloane Lab was led by University College London (UCL), which oversaw the research, technical trajectory and alignment (including ethical oversight and data protection) of the project as a whole, along with administrative and budgetary management and reporting on the project to AHRC and the Towards a National Collection directorate. Further particulars of UCL's contributions to every work package of this project are given below.

Project collaborators were the British Museum (BM) and Natural History Museum (NHM), where Co-Investigators Jeremy Hill (BM) and Mark Carine (NHM) oversaw the execution of their respective institutions' deliverables for the project and supervised the Sloane Lab-funded project staff hired by their institutions.

The NHM team worked closely with the UCL technical team to carry out data review, catalogue data cleaning and enhancement, and created a single data set of natural history specimens for data mobilisation. They also led and/or contributed to publications on the mobilisation of data held in Sloane's copy of *Historia Platarum* and cataloguing of Sloane's botanical collections. In addition, the team hosted a TECHNE DTP Racial Justice placement student who directly made use of data generated through the project to research plants in Sloane's collections that were used by enslaved women to control their fertility as an act of resistance.

The team members in BM likewise worked with the UCL technical team to carry out data review, catalogue data cleaning and enhancement and to encode new transcriptions of Sloane Manuscripts. They led the research and preparation for the touring exhibition hosted by Down County Museum in Northern Ireland and Ceredigion Museum in Aberystwyth, Wales. They also led on permanent display changes in BM. Finally, they contributed to publications on the absences contained in Sloane's collection and on digital collection infrastructures. UCL, NHM and BM all supervised community fellows.

Project Partners

British Library	<p>Advise, including review of and input into project documentation, quarterly meetings, and active engagement/facilitation with Library colleagues and others outside the project.</p> <p>General curatorial and project support from teams within Western Heritage Collections responsible for managing Sloane collections.</p> <p>Provision of existing manuscript catalogue data from the Explore Archives and Manuscripts catalogue.</p> <p>Provision of catalogue records for printed books held by the British Library, derived and enhanced from the Sloane Printed Books catalogue, and supplied as MARC XML.</p>
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Community Archives & Heritage Group	<p>Share experiences and explore how the different solutions developed by the project could address similar challenges and inform the future strategy and work of CAHG.</p> <p>Encourage members of Community Archives to actively engage in the project's participatory research sessions and attend meetings where the learning from the research was shared.</p> <p>Advise on the project's dissemination activities aimed at Community Archives.</p> <p>Advertise the Fellowships over CAHG networks.</p>
Collecting the West (Australian Research Council funded project)	Meet with the Sloane Lab team annually for the purpose of knowledge exchange and with the potential to develop more connections with the Sloane Lab team and their partners in Australia. Collaborate on Melbourne workshop.
Down County Museum (Northern Ireland)	<p>Host a travelling exhibition of key artefacts relating to Hans Sloane to help local people re-engage with the diverse aspects of Hans Sloane's legacy.</p> <p>The Museum used the Lab to encourage its existing and new audiences to explore various themes relating to the lifetime and context of Sloane that are relevant to our lives today, including natural themes such as biodiversity, and cultural themes such as the legacy of colonialism and the slave trade.</p> <p>A loan exhibition on Hans Sloane enabled the museum to explore all aspects of museology, using both the digital Sloane Lab and its own collections to stimulate interest, debate, and audience participation.</p>
University of Oxford, Department of Plant Sciences University of Oxford, Gardens, Libraries and Museums Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh National Museum of Scotland Historic Environment Scotland National Galleries of Scotland	<p>Knowledge exchange on sharing digital collections, using digital tools to support the digitisation of collections information, and learning how better support different people to use the digital collections.</p> <p>Explore how the different solutions developed by the project could address similar challenges and inform future work and strategy.</p> <p>Contribution of staff time and potential for integration with other initiatives.</p>

Staffing Structure

Professor Julianne Nyhan FRHistS (Professor Emeritus of Digital Humanities, UCL; Chair and Professor of Humanities Data Science and Methodology, TU Darmstadt; Managing Director of the Institute of History, TU Darmstadt) **Principal Investigator** and intellectual lead of the project overall. Nyhan had overall

responsibility for the research, technical and participatory direction of the project and for the line management of UCL-based Research Fellows. Nyhan maintained a bird's eye view of the project, its progress and direction overall, tracking research execution and trajectory. **Nyhan and all Co-Investigators** also contributed to research output writing, dissemination and delivery, including presenting the project at high-profile international events.

Dr Andrew Flinn (Reader in Archival Studies and Oral History, UCL), **Deputy Principal Investigator and Co-Investigator** of the project. As Deputy Principal Investigator, Flinn was the intellectual lead of the project's overall approach to participatory co-creation and ethical working practices. As Co-Investigator, he co-led the participatory work package, supervising the work of the Participatory Consultant (Dr Alda Terracciano), shaping the project's participatory strategy, implementation, and evaluation with Dr Nina Pearlman and Nyhan. Known for his scholarship on independent and community archives, Flinn also opened pathways for the project to connect with community archive and heritage groups.

Dr Andreas Vlachidis (Associate Professor in Information Science, UCL), **Co-Investigator** was the intellectual lead of the project's technical elaboration, execution and delivery. He supervised, with input from Nyhan, the Research Fellow's implementation of the project's technical architecture and led the research on methods for integrating the dispersed Sloane collection under a unified Knowledge Base. He also contributed to the work of participatory design, liaising with the relevant team member in an iterative process that sought to incorporate input into the design and development of the Knowledge Base and other connected dissemination of data retrieval and visualisation.

Dr Nina Pearlman, Co-Investigator (Head of UCL Art Collections, UCL), supervised the work of the Participatory PDRA (Marco Humbel) and co-led the project's participatory strategy, implementation, and evaluation with Dr Andrew Flinn, working closely with Nyhan. Given her extensive experience in the cultural heritage sector, Dr Pearlman also opened pathways to dispersed and living collections.

Dr Mark Carine, Co-Investigator (Principal Curator in Charge, Algae, Fungi, and Plants Division, Natural History Museum), is the curator responsible for Sloane's botanical collections. He supervised the NHM PDRA (Dr Victoria Pickering) and oversaw the mobilisation of the NHM data with Sloane's taxonomic index to the herbarium as well as case study research.

Dr J D Hill, Co-Investigator (Head of Research, The Directorate, The British Museum), supervised the BM PDRF (Dr Alicia Hughes), Programme Coordinator (hired in year two) and BM Consultant (Dr Kim Sloan), was responsible for coordinating the overall strategy and implementation of the BM touring exhibition and for communications regarding data exchange between the British Museum, UCL, Natural History Museum, British Library and other partners as relevant. He also facilitated conversations with relevant partners in Australia and the UK.

Dr Sushma Jansari, Co-Investigator (Tabo Foundation Curator: South Asia, The British Museum), was responsible for supporting the BM PDRF (Dr Alicia Hughes) in the delivery of community engagement work for the touring exhibition.

Dr Daniele Metilli, Research Fellow in Advanced Data Architectures for Digital Humanities (UCL), was responsible for the Sloane Lab metadata mapping, semantic data modelling, knowledge base design and development, including ontologies, linked data, and graph databases.

Dr Foteini Valeonti, Research Fellow in Systems Development and Research (UCL), was responsible for executing computational components and interfaces, enabling programmatic access to digital collections, data aggregation and federation and front-end (application) development.

Dr Jawad Sadek, Senior Research Fellow in Artificial Intelligence and Natural Language Processing (UCL), undertook research on NLP and AI to implement solutions for information extraction, automatic handwritten text recognition and semantic enrichment of museum data and cultural heritage collections.

Dr Marco Humbel, Research Fellow in Participatory Research and Collections as Data (UCL), was responsible for contributing to participatory research and design; for facilitating a series of participatory events with heritage organisations, and planning community fellowships.

Dr Victoria Pickering, Research Fellow (Natural History Museum), was responsible for mobilising Sloane's taxonomic index to the NHM's Sloane herbarium; executing machine actionable versions of Sloane catalogues, case study research, and supporting the community fellows.

Dr Alicia Hughes, Project Curator (The British Museum), was engaged in mobilising data on Sir Hans Sloane's collections held at the British Museum, as well as researching case studies on Sloane's collections and supporting the community fellows. Alicia was also lead curator for the touring exhibition and changes to a permanent display at the BM.

Dr Kim Sloan, Historical Consultant (The British Museum), is an acknowledged expert on Sloane and PI on previous AHRC and Leverhulme-funded projects on Sloane's collection, oversaw the transcription and encoding of the BM's Sloane manuscript catalogues, advised on the creation of the Data Atlas, on the touring exhibition and permanent redisplay and supported the community fellows.

Dr Alda Terracciano, Community Consultant (UCL), provided consultancy on the elaboration of participatory methodologies and instruments for working with diverse communities and for the planning and delivery of engagement events.

Dr Isobel MacDonald, Research Fellow (UCL), assisted with mobilisation of BM data and provided support for research outputs across work teams.

Rosalyn Tyler, Exhibition Programme Manager (The British Museum), supported delivery of the touring exhibition programme in year two.

Simon Boulter, Exhibition Programme Manager (The British Museum), supported delivery of the touring exhibition programme in year three.

Hanna James, Project Administrator (UCL), served as the first point of contact for all stakeholders, and coordinated all participatory events and communication channels. She also assisted with reporting to AHRC and documentation of findings of participatory events.

Ciara Adeniyi-Jones, Project Administrator (UCL), as successor to Hanna James, served as the first point of contact for all stakeholders, and coordinated all participatory events and communication channels. She also assisted with reporting to AHRC and documentation of findings of participatory events.

Overall Programme

Meetings and Events

Meetings and Workshops

Dates	Description	Attendees
14 October 2021	Meeting with the Royal Society (RS) to introduce the Sloane Lab and catch up with RS on the development of their digitisation programme. RS offered to do a survey of the Sloane material and was interested in joining the Advisory Board for the wider consultation and contribute to the project.	Attendees included RS Head of Library and Information Services, Digital Resources Manager, Sloane Lab PI and Historical Consultant of Sloane Lab.
16 December 2021	A follow-up meeting with the Royal Society (RS) to discuss Sloane data provided by RS.	Attendees included the Head of Library and Information Services, Digital Resources Manager, and Technical Lead of Sloane Lab.
14 January 2022	Meeting with Down County Museum Curator and CEO/Founder of Sir Hans Sloane Centre to discuss the scope of the partnership and the role of Down County Museum in the touring exhibition.	Attendees included Down County Museum Curator and CEO/Founder of Sir Hans Sloane Centre, British Museum Head of National Programmes, and Sloane Lab team members.
19 January 2022	Initial Meeting with Project Partners and Advisory Board. The purpose of the meeting was to introduce Sloane Lab to the partner organisations and Advisory Board and to invite support from them. The team explained the background of the Towards a National Collection programme, as well as the research approach of the project.	Total attendance 36, including 26 from partner organisations and the Sloane Lab Advisory Board members, some of whom were located internationally.
16 February 2022	Meeting with British Museum and Natural History Museum colleagues to introduce the Sloane Lab participatory and engagement plan and consultations.	Attendees include Natural History Museum UX Manager, British Museum Community Engagement Consultant, British Museum Head of National Programmes, and Sloane Lab participatory team. Total attendance 10, including Head of Western Heritage Collections and Curators.

24 March 2022	Meeting with British Library (BL) to discuss how BL could engage with the Sloane Lab project, also the areas of involvement and consultations. The various BL curator also gave overviews on the Sloane materials housing in BL, and some technical practicalities.	Total attendance 10, including Head of Western Heritage Collections and Curators.
20 April 2022	Meeting with Australian Project Partner, Collecting the West (CTW). Following a brief overview of both the technical and participatory methods of Sloane Lab, the group discussed the possible knowledge exchange areas, including overlaps of the two projects on how to handle and aggregate data and shared experience on community engagement.	Total attendance 11, including three from the CTW.
4 May 2022	Year 1 Advisory Board meeting. Apart from reporting on work packages, the project team sought the expertise and experience of the Advisory Board in connection with a number of questions, such as best practices in the integration of dispersed data sets and including the voices of small heritage organisations and non-hegemonic communities.	Total attendance 26, including 12 from the Sloane Lab Advisory Board.
5-6 May 2022	Jeremy Hill (Co-I) and British Museum Head of National Programmes Northern Ireland visit. He met with Down County Museum CEO and other staff for Sloane Lab travel exhibition planning.	Down County Museum and Sir Hans Sloane Centre staff members.
20 May 2022	Meeting with UCL Copyright Officer (referred by Advisory Board member) for consultation on CC Licence and IP of reusing Sloane Lab materials.	Attendance: UCL Copyright Officer, PI and Project Administrator.
June to July 2022	Interview consultations with curators, archivists, librarians and IT specialists on collection data infrastructure development.	18 participants
3 October 2022	Sloane Lab Pilot Workshop for exploring participants, questions and activities for participatory co-design.	Sloane Lab team
23 October 2022	Searching for Jamaican plants in the Sloane Lab. A half day digital jam workshop designed by Alda Terracciano and produced in collaboration with Marco Humbel as part of the Natural History Museum Explorers Family Festival.	Target group: British Caribbean people interested in plants. Number of participants: 20

2 November 2022	<p>Meeting with Australian Project Partner, Collecting the West (CTW). Initial exploratory consultation with Collecting the West team. Members of each Sloane Lab work package attended and key issues around collections as data, data-driven collections research, and the design of digital collection-based resources were discussed. Possible formats for the workshop and possible dates in 2023 were discussed.</p>	Attendance: Alistair Paterson (CTW), members of Sloane Lab.
8 November 2022	<p>The Sloane Lab data challenge: engaging with and aggregating our challenging pasts, Central London (UCL Bloomsbury campus). Focus group and workshop to explore innovative approaches and technological tools to manage, query, and visualize the data, including the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base and the Sloane Lab Data Atlas. Designed and produced by Alda Terracciano in collaboration with Marco Humbel, Foteini Valeonti, Daniele Metilli, Jawad Sadek, and Andreas Vlachidis as part of the MTSR Conference.</p>	<p>Target group: experts in data modelling, metadata, & semantics. Number of participants: 19</p>
7 December 2022	<p>Connecting Jamaican plants across Sloane collections, Central London (UCL Bloomsbury campus). Workshop to identify what expert users might want to do with data from various Sloane's datasets and to explore the interoperability of the Sloane Lab database with external digital collections, using a selection of specimen from Sloane's <i>Voyage to Jamaica</i>. Designed by Alda Terracciano and produced in collaboration with Marco Humbel and Vicky Pickering.</p>	<p>Target group: Sloane experts. Number of participants: 8</p>
21 February 2023	<p>Who holds the data? Connecting cultivated plants to specimens in the Sloane Lab. Consultation with representatives from the Heritage Seed Library to co-produce a workshop with members of community heritage organisations. Designed and produced by Alda Terracciano.</p>	<p>Target group: community heritage organisations. Number of participants: 4</p>
26 February 2023	<p>Meeting with Australian Project Partner, Collecting the West (CTW). Meeting with the wider CTW team. It was confirmed that the Knowledge Exchange event will take place on 22-24 November 2023 in Melbourne, Australia and will be hosted by Deakin University. The selection of Sloane Lab</p>	Attendance: Wider CTW team (four members), Sloane Lab members Alicia Hughes, Jeremy Hill, Ciara Adeniyi-Jones.

	team members to contribute to the event was made.	
5 April 2023	Meeting with Australian Project Partner, Collecting the West (CTW). Update on planning for the workshop and further discuss ideas.	
19 April 2023	Who holds the data? Connecting plants to specimens in the Sloane Lab. Participatory workshop in collaboration with Heritage Seed Library.	Target group: botanists, gardeners, seed heritage guardians & growers. Number of participants: 22
9 May 2023	Down County Museum workshop	Target group: local communities in Killyleagh and Downpatrick. Number of participants: 12
10 May 2023	Meeting with Advisory Board members	Internal workshop
25 May 2023	Conference planning meeting with Australian Project Partner, Collecting the West (CTW)	
20 July 2023	Sloane Lab interoperability: Exploring Northern Ireland's past and present global connections through Sloane collections. Participatory workshop in collaboration with Sir Hans Sloane Centre & British Museum.	Target group: local communities in Killyleagh and Downpatrick. Number of participants: 21
6-7 September 2023	TaNc Sloane Lab European Knowledge Exchange Event, TU Darmstadt Focus group on collections as data infrastructure development with invited participants.	Approximately 50 people with international and professional reach. Focus group participants: 10
8 October 2023	Searching for Jamaican Plants in the Sloane Lab Natural History Museum Explorers Family Festival: The Nature of the Caribbean Islands.	Target group: British Caribbean people interested in plants. Number of participants: 22
26 October 2023	Towards a National Collection-organised equalities workshop with West of Scotland Equality Council.	Internal workshop
8 November 2023	Project update meeting with Sloane Lab, Advisory Board & Heritage Partners.	Internal workshop

22-23 November 2023	Researching the Future of Museum Collections’ workshop hosted by Deakin University Melbourne. Focus group on collections as data infrastructure development with invited participants.	Workshop attendees: approx. 50 people with international and professional reach. Focus group participants: 8
28 November 2023	Sloane Lab meeting with Decolonising the Archives	
7 December 2023	Meeting with Victoria Kingston to discuss website updates	
7 December 2023	Meeting with Tiffany Ong, Alessandra Esposito discussion on potential collaboration	
31 January 2024	Preliminary meeting with Dr Tiara Roxanne (Sloane Lab Data Ethics seminar/workshop)	
1 February 2024	Knowledge Base (KB) User Experience Testing Lab session 1	Target group: Potential future KB user group, identified through survey. Number of participants: 11
7 February 2024	Planning meeting with Decolonising the Archives	
9 February 2024	Meeting with Towards a National Collection Discovery project ‘Our Heritage, Our Stories’	
20 February 2024	Knowledge Base User Experience Testing Lab session 2	Target group: Community Fellows and Decolonising the Archives team. Number of participants: 7
2 February 2024	Meeting with Decolonising the Archive to plan workshop (AT)	
13 March 2024	Meeting with Decolonising the Archive to plan workshop (AT)	
26 March 2024	Exploring the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base. Participatory workshop in collaboration with Decolonising the Archive.	Target group: Decolonising the Archives community. Number of participants: 20
2 May 2024	Sloane Lab Data Ethics Seminar with Dr Tiara Roaxanne	Internal workshop for Sloane Lab team members.
8 May 2024	Meeting with Advisory Board	Internal workshop
8 June 2024	Exploring the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base. Participatory workshop in collaboration with Decolonising the Archive.	Target group: Decolonising the Archives community.

Conference Presentations, Talks and Interviews

Dates	Description	Attendance
13 October 2021	Co-I Nina Pearlman presented at a UCL Institute of Collections Webinar and introduced Sloane Lab internally.	Attendance: less than 50 with local and professional reach.
18 November 2021	Co-I Mark Carine co-organised a workshop with Queen Mary University: <i>Disciplinary and the early-modern herbarium - A one-day research workshop</i> . He referred to the Sloane Lab and underpinned the multidisciplinary nature of the project, an opportunity to engage researchers from different disciplines.	Attendance: less than 50 with local and professional reach.
3 December 2021	Julianne Nyhan, Sloane Lab PI, presented at Universität Bern seminar <i>Digitality/Digital Culture(s)</i> . Presentation topic: Loss, absence, and contestation in Digital Humanities through the lens of the collection of Hans Sloane (1660-1753).	Attendance: For PhD students and advanced Master students at the University of Bern. More than 50 with international and professional reach.
27 January 2022	Julianne Nyhan chaired and presented at The Society for the History of Collections special meetings <i>New Perspectives on Sloane</i> to provide a platform for new research on Sloane.	Attendance: more than 50 with academics and students.
19 May 2022	Communicating Colonial Legacies Workshop. A half day workshop organised by Towards a National Collection (TaNC) and hosted by Sloane Lab in UCL.	Attendance 32, including delegates from other Discovery Projects and TaNC/AHRC.
5-10 Jun 2022	Natural History Museum PDRA Victoria Pickering presented at the conference for the Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections (SPNHC) Poster Session. Abstract title: <i>Mobilising data in the Natural History Museum's historical botanical collection</i> .	Attendance: The estimated number of participants is 450 with international reach.
10 June 2022	A deeper look at the Semantic Web, pt. 2 – The Sloane Lab. Daniele Metilli presented the Sloane Lab in the context of the CLARIN workshop series 'Digital Philology Meets Computational Linguistics', organised by the Venice Centre of Digital and Public Humanities at the University of Venice.	Attendance: less than 50 people of professional practitioners and students.
23 June 2022	Nina Pearlman invited to panel discussion at the EdTechX summit in London. Panel discussion at the EdTechX summit in London that explores new	Attendance: less than 50 professional practitioners, policymakers, industry, and students with international reach.

	trends at the intersection of education and Tech with respect to VR/AR and the metaverse.	
1 July 2022	Vicky Pickering presented a short talk at the Natural History Museum's monthly Collections and Culture Research theme meeting to introduce the Sloane Lab.	Attendance: less than 50 Natural History Museum colleagues.
5-8 July 2022	Universeum 2022 (Belgium) – Poster section presentation of conference paper 'Interrogating collections' contested and challenging past through the Sloane (GLAM) Lab' (J. Nyhan, A. Vlachidis, A. Flinn, N. Pearlman, M. Humbel, D. Metilli, J. Sadek, F. Valeonti, M. Carine, V. Pickering & A. Terracciano). Research Fellows, Daniele Metilli and Marco Humbel are bursary awardees of the Universeum Pre-Conference Training Workshop (5-8 July). They co-presented the outcomes of the workshop.	Attendance: about 100 with international reach from the university, museums and archives sectors.
15 July 2022	Digital Humanities Summer School at Oxford - DHOxSS2022 (11 July 2022 – 15 July 2022). PI Julianne Nyhan presented keynote at Keble College Oxford. 'Thinking through the place of absence in the grand challenges of the Digital Humanities and Humanities Data Science'.	Attendance: more than 50 with students and DH scholars.
8-10 September 2022	The Digital Humanities Congress Sep 2022. Deborah Leem, Andreas Vlachidis, Prof Julianne Nyhan (PI) - Presented paper 'Sir Han Sloane's Information Architecture: From TEI to CSV for Data Analysis.'	Attendance: approximately 60 professional practitioners, policymakers, and postgraduate students. National reach.
12-16 September 2022	EUSN 2022 London, 6th European Conference on Social Networks. The Sloane Lab team (Daniele Metilli; Andreas Vlachidis; Marco Humbel; Victoria Pickering; Mark Carine; Kim Sloan; Julianne Nyhan), presented paper 'Towards a network analysis of Hans Sloane's collection: A preliminary study' at 6th European Conference on Social Networks 12-16 September 2022 in University of Greenwich, London, UK.	Attendance: approximately 85 professional practitioners and postgraduate students. International reach.
15-16 September 2022	Bauhin Conference 2022 at University of Basel. Co-I Dr Mark Carine presented 'Documenting, understanding and opening the botanical collections of Hans Sloane (1660-1753)' at the conference. He also served as one of the Scientific Committee members for the conference.	Attendance: Approximately 100 professional practitioners. International reach.

21 October 2022	Interdisciplinary creative engagements with collections at UCL and beyond. Nina Pearlman was a guest speaker presenting the Sloane Lab in the context of a session on public and private collections to undergraduate fine art students at the University of East London (UEL) BA Fine Art.	Attendance: less than 10 local undergraduate students.
14 November 2022	Der Schöne-Vortrag, titled 'Mind the Gap: Data absence, data silence, and data bias'. PI Prof. Julianne Nyhan gave the Der Schöne-Vortrag, titled 'Mind the Gap: Data absence, data silence, and data bias' on 14th November 2022 at The Technical University of Berlin (TU Berlin).	Attendance: approximately 100 professional practitioners, students, policymakers. International reach and engagement with the media as a channel to wider audiences.
10 January 2023	Bridging worlds: collaborative case studies in technology and art collections at UCL. Nina Pearlman presented the Sloane Lab in the context of UCL case studies where collections meet technology at TRAN(S)MISSIONS how multimediality shapes interdisciplinary research in the field of Italian and Visual Culture Studies 3rd edition. Winter School.	Attendance: approximately 25 people, primarily professional practitioners and students. International reach.
27 March 2023	Challenges and Opportunities of Semantic Modelling and Enrichment in Small and Large Museum collections. Andreas Vlachidis presented at the International Seminar on <i>Semantic Web, Cultural Heritage, and Art Historical Knowledge: Conceptual Models, Ontologies, and Epistemological Implications</i> .	Attendance: approximately 75 professional practitioners-academics and GLAM sector experts. International reach.
18 May 2023	Museum Analytics event. Sloane Lab: Domain vocabularies for semantic interoperability of museum collections, authored by Andreas Vlachidis, Daniele Metilli.	Attendance: less than 50 with local and professional reach.
25 May 2023	Sloane Lab Symposium Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kathleen Lawther 'People make the data: Museum Makers, people-centred cataloguing and collections as data' • Florence Okoye 'Approaches for anti-colonial narratives through digital collections' 	Attendance: more than 50 with international and professional reach.
1 June 2023	Sloane Lab Symposium Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Koraljka Golub 'Subject access in online information services for humanities: the case of LGBTQI fiction' • Inna Kizhner 'Exploring epistemic bias in museum collections' 	Attendance: more than 50 with international and professional reach.

8 June 2023	<p>Sloane Lab Symposium Series</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lucille Junkere ‘Cultural Colours Jamaica’ • Benjamin Lee ‘Reimagining Search and Discovery for Digital collections with Machine Learning’ 	Attendance: more than 50 with international and professional reach.
15 June 2023	<p>Sloane Lab Symposium Series</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jane Collings ‘The Shortcomings of and Opportunities for archival Cataloguing to Create a Fuller Picture of Our Histories’ 	Attendance: more than 50 with international and professional reach.
22 June 2023	<p>Sloane Lab Symposium Series</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rosemary Grennan ‘Leftovers Digital Archive: Somewhere between automation and the homemade’ • Amalia S. Levi ‘Archival Dependencies: The Cascading Violence of Colonial Records’ 	Attendance: more than 50 with international and professional reach.
10-14 July 2023	<p>DH2023, Graz Austria.</p> <p>The Sloane lab has accepted an invitation to partake in a panel presentation at the annual conference, titled ‘Looking back to build future shared collections: reports from the Sloane Lab’, authored by Marco Humbel, Foteini Valeonti, Daniele Metilli, Jawad Sadek, Alda Terracciano, Victoria Pickering, Alicia Hughes, Andreas Vlachidis, Nina Pearlman, Andrew Flinn, Mark Carine, Kim Sloan and Julianne Nyhan.</p>	Attendance: approximately 80-100 professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and students with international reach.
10-14 July 2023	<p>DH2023, Graz Austria.</p> <p>Daniele Metilli presented a paper titled: ‘Beyond data borders: The Sloane Lab experience’.</p>	Attendance: approximately 80-100 professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and students with international reach.
1 September 2023	<p>XVII OPTIMA meeting in Erice.</p> <p>Conference poster: ‘The Mediterranean world of Hans Sloane: insights from the Sloane Lab’ authored by Marc Carine.</p>	Attendance: less than 50 with professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and students with international reach.
14 September 2023	<p>Encountering Children of Empire Symposium (NTS & Beniba Centre for Slavery Studies).</p> <p>‘Looking back to Build Future Shared Collections Project at the British Museum’</p>	Attendance: less than 50 with regional community reach.
23 November 2023	<p>Sloane Lab presentation at Collecting the West Knowledge Exchange Event, Melbourne Australia titled ‘Sloane Lab: Why look back to build future shared collections?’, authored by Alicia Hughes, Vicky Pickering, Marco Humbel, Daniele Metilli, JD Hill, Nina Pearlman, Alda Terracciano.</p>	Attendance: approximately 50 professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and students with international reach.

30 November 2023	17:15 Colloquium of the ETH Library Zurich. 'Collections as Data Infrastructures: Perspectives from the United Kingdom.', authored by Marco Humbel.	Attendance: approximately 80-100 professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and students with international reach.
20 January 2024	Down County Museum Exhibition Programme 'For the curious and interested talk'	Attendance: approximately 51-100 members of the public with a regional reach.
28 February 2024	Towards a National Collection Discovery Project Webinar. Marco Humbel gave a presentation titled 'Digital Infrastructure – Collection data infrastructures: Latent challenges as dynamics in the heritage sector'.	Attendance: 131 professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and students with international reach.
29 February 2024	British Museum staff breakfast: 'Sloane Lab: Why look back to build future shared collections'.	101-500 British Museum staff members.
March 2024	Sloane Tour at Natural History Museum (NHM) with Inclusion, Diversity, Equality, Action (IDEA) group.	36 NHM members of staff.
2 March 2024	Down County Museum Exhibition Programme: 'Sir Hans Sloane's <i>Vegetable Substances</i> '.	11-50 people. Regional, public audience.
19 March 2024	Towards a National Collection Discovery Project Webinar. Foteini Valeonti gave a presentation titled 'Decentralising Digital Humanities'	Attendance: 92 professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and student swith international reach.
17 April 2024	CAA-GR Conference 2024 Andreas Vlachidis presented at the conference the paper 'The Collection Unit as the Integral Component in Development of a Data Atlas of Complex Cultural Heritage Landscapes'	Attendance: more than 50 with international and professional reach.
22 April 2024	MA Digital Humanities, Linnaeus University, Sweden – Invited Lecture Andreas Vlachidis delivered a lecture titled "'Exploring complex cultural spaces: The Sloane Lab case study'	Attendance: less than 50 with regional and professional reach.
20-21 April 2024	Workshop of Alliance of Early Universal Museums, Halle	Attendance: less than 50 with international and professional reach.
30 April 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anna Sofia Lippolis (Community Fellow & University of Bologna) 'An Ontology for Multivocality: Embracing Diverse Perspectives in Machine-Readable Form' 	Attendance: Attendance: more than 50 with international and professional reach.
23 April 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wolfgang Göderle (Max-Planck-Institute) and David Fleischhacker (Technical University of Graz) 'Enhancing OCR with 	Attendance: approximately 40-50 students and professional practitioners with international reach.

	AI for Historical Documents: A Breakthrough in the Research on Habsburg State-Manuals'	
30 April 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gayle Chong Kwan (Community Fellow & GCK) 'Travelling Taxonomies' 	Attendance: approximately 40-50 students and professional practitioners with international reach.
7 May 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bethany Johnstone (UCL London) 'Whirling around a digital future' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners with international reach.
8 May 2024	Chinese University of Hong Kong, CUHK Faculty of Arts and Digital Scholarship Lab – Seminar. Andreas Vlachidis delivered the seminar 'Semantic Data Modelling Experiences and Advances in Cultural Heritage Collections: A Decade and a Half of Using and Extending CIDOC-CRM'	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners with international reach.
9 May 2024	Chinese University of Hong Kong, CUHK Faculty of Arts and Digital Scholarship Lab – Seminar Andreas Vlachidis delivered the workshop 'Knowledge base technologies and semantics for interrogating complex data environments: A case study of the Sloane Lab's Cultural Heritage Collection'	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
14 May 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stella Sylaiou (International Hellenic University) 'Leveraging XR for the Promotion of Art and Cultural Heritage' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
21 May 2024	Julianne Nyhan, invited talk: 'Contesting, remaking and reimagining absence among and with digital methods: a 3-project based examination', Max Planck Institut fuer Wissenschaft Geschichte.	Attendance: less than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
21 May 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dorothy Kyagaba Sebbowa (Community Fellow & Makerere University) 'Anti-Colonial Annotations of Sloane Jamaican references' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
28 May 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arjun Sanyal (University of Himachal Pradesh) 'Enframing narratives & post-Fordist Global South Digital Humanities ecosystem' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
4 June 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phillip Rhys Olney (Community Fellow) 'The Display Strategies of Hans Sloane's Collection As 'Bifocal Data' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.

11 June 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gethin Rees (Community Fellow & British Library) 'Finding Alternatives to Web Mercator in the Geography of Sloane's Collection' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
12 June 2024	UCL Innovation & Enterprise - Transform: Creating impact through knowledge exchange. Andreas Vlachidis presented the paper 'Aggregating Disperse Cultural Heritage Collections and Managing Intellectual Property'.	Attendance less than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
18 June 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rosalind White (Community Fellow & University of Birmingham) 'In the Margins of Early Modern Science: Pioneering Women in Sloane's 'Paper Museum' Hannah Cusworth (Community Fellow & English Heritage) 'Bringing Sloane into Conversation with Blackness' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
25 June 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rosemary Grennan (Community Fellow & May Day Rooms) 'Building Common Ownership and Shared Archival Practices' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
2 July 2024	Sloane Lab HDSM (TU Darmstadt) Webinar Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brian Wingenroth (Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health) and Cecilia Tomori (Johns Hopkins School of Nursing) 'Digital Tools for Addressing a Public Health Crisis' 	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
7 August 2024	DH 2024 Arlington, VA Paper presentation titled 'Investigating absences in cultural heritage collections: A Sloane Lab case study authored by Daniele Metilli, Alicia Hughes and Andreas Vlachidis'	Attendance: approximately 80-100 professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and student with international reach.
8 August 2024	DH 2024 Arlington, VA Paper presentation titled 'Towards International Perspectives on Collection Data Infrastructure Development', authored by Marco Humbel, Nina Pearlman, JD Hill, Andrew Flinn and Julianne Nyhan.	Attendance: approximately 80-100 professional practitioners, policy makers, industry and students with international reach.
4 October 2024	DARIAH-EU Friday Frontiers Autumn Series. Julianne Nyhan, Andreas Vlachidis, and Alda Terracciano delivered the webinar titled 'Innovations for a Unified Digital Collection: The Sloane Lab Journey to Unlocking the Past and Shaping the Future'.	Attendance: less than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.

31 October 2024	<p>International Workshop on Semantic Web and Ontology Design for Cultural Heritage, SWODCH 2024.</p> <p>Andreas Vlachidis was invited to give the keynote lecture, 'The Sloane Lab Knowledge Base as an example of semantic unification and interrogation of historic catalogues and GLAM collections'</p>	Attendance: more than 50 with professional practitioners and international reach.
20 November 2024	<p>Towards a National Collection Conference 2024 'The Sloane Lab: History with innovation in shared collection development'</p> <p>Julianne Nyhan gave a keynote presentation, chaired by JD Hill.</p>	Attendance: 221 in-person and 154 online.
21 November 2024	<p>Towards a National Collection Conference 2024 'Co-creation' panel discussion with Unpath'd Waters Discovery Project team.</p> <p>Dr Andrew Flinn, University College London; Dr Alda Terracciano, University College London.</p>	Attendance: 221 in-person and 154 online.

Research Approach

Sloane Lab sought to answer the following research questions:

- How can museums, libraries, archives and galleries (GLAMs) use digital technology to link their collections together in ways that make it easier for different people, both specialists and interested publics, to find the information they want?
- How can digital technology help us tell new stories about what can be rediscovered and reimagined by linking collections?
- How can we make specialist users and members of the public more aware of the contested nature and histories of museum collections?
- What is the role of digital tools in foregrounding overlooked or hidden processes, like imperialism, colonialism, the transatlantic trade in enslaved people, loss and destruction, that have shaped the national collection?
- Who gets to contribute to, and shape, research on how memory institutions can reach across their institutional boundaries, subject-specialities and even countries to better engage their varied audiences?
- And how can heritage institutions select the most useful technologies from the many that are available for digitising, releasing and interlinking their collections?

The research we undertook in response to these questions was pursued across three principal strands – which were intellectually and practically interconnected but discussed separately below for the purposes of clarity – namely, technical elaboration and aggregation; participatory engagement; and collections research.

Technical Elaboration and Aggregation

The technical elaboration and aggregation pursued by the Sloane Lab technical team can be conceptualised as a process of retro-engineering the envisaged public-facing, open-access Sloane Lab, containing the data, tools and services to support cross-collection search, digitally augmented exploration and reuse of digital cultural heritage collections. Working from the vision to the actual implementation, the following technical steps were identified as essential to delivering the Lab:

- Instantiation of computational infrastructure and architecture to support the Lab.
- Identification of the Collection's dataset landscape, access and retrieval of dataset manual, automatically or semi automatically.
- Iterative elaboration of a unified data model and ontological schema, and mapping of Sloane's data to the adopted schema.
- Data mobilisation, cleaning and enrichment
- Ongoing ingestion of data into the Knowledge Graph (triple store).
- Development of query and visualisation dashboard, including tools and services that allow that data to be Findable, Cross-searchable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
- Iterative user-testing of interfaces and approaches.
- Publishing and deployment.

We will now discuss the most substantive of these steps in further detail.

Identification of the Collection's Dataset Landscape, Access and Retrieval of Dataset Manually, Automatically or Semi Automatically

The records that describe the Sloane collection are many and complex. They include some 40 manuscript catalogues compiled by Sloane and his assistants and the digital and analogue records of the national institutions mentioned above that describe Sloane's collection. They also include historical resources such as collection guides, correspondence, minutes from when Sloane served as Secretary of the Royal Society (1693 to 1713), as well as modern resources such as digital surrogates, digitally born documents and databases.

Decision-making process and instruments were accordingly required to identify and select records to be included in (and excluded from) the Sloane Lab. Finding a dearth of existing instruments to support this, the project responded by developing a methodological framework, the Collection Data Atlas, for mapping the informational landscape of complex cultural heritage collections that span institutions, information systems, epochs and materialities. Our application of this framework to Sloane Lab resulted in the Sloane Data Atlas, the first such synthesis and visualisation of the complex bibliographic and data environment of the collection of Sir Hans Sloane, the founding collection of the UK heritage sector. Sloane Lab's Data Atlas has evolved into a robust process for visualising and ultimately understanding complex data environments that feature datasets dispersed across different information systems and infrastructures. This approach has allowed us to navigate Sloane Lab's data environment more seamlessly, facilitating better decision-making during the project. As a methodological instrument the data atlas can be beneficial to large-scale digital projects that deal with complex data environments and has been made available on GitHub as an open-source project (<https://github.com/sloanelab-org/data-atlas>).

Iterative Elaboration of a Unified Data Model and Ontological Schema, and Mapping of Sloane's Data to the Adopted Schema

Through the Sloane Lab, we sought to facilitate access to the historical and contemporary knowledge contained in the Sloane collections through an interactive knowledge environment (the Knowledge Base). At the centre of this work was, accordingly, the elaboration of the Sloane Lab data model.

The data contained in the Knowledge Base is represented in line with Semantic Web standards, in particular, RDF, RDFS, and OWL. The Sloane Lab data model is built on top of the CIDOC CRM reference ontology. This is an authoritative ontology for representing cultural heritage data, developed by the International Council of Museums, and recognised by ISO 21127:2014. In addition to CIDOC CRM, Sloane Lab used CRMdig, an extension of the CIDOC CRM, for the representation of the datasets, and we have taken inspiration from the approaches of the Parthenos Entities Model (FORTH-ICS, 2018) and the Unpath'd Waters project (Sloane et al., 2022). Other ontologies that are relevant for our purposes are CRMgeo (Hiebel et al., 2017) for geographical information, Bio CRM (Tuominen et al., 2017) for biographical information, and CRMsci (Doerr et al., 2018) and CRMinf (Doerr et al., 2023) for modelling inference processes. When extending CIDOC CRM, we followed the recommended practices of adding new classes and properties only when necessary, connecting them to the existing taxonomies of classes and properties, and relying on E55 Type system whenever possible.

Some of the most significant challenges in the development of the Sloane Lab data model and Knowledge Base were the handling of uncertainty, the multivocality of the collection (e.g., conflicting data from different records about the same object), data absences (i.e., gaps in the records), the difficulty of classifying objects, and the fact that some of the objects described in the historical catalogues do not survive. Another important challenge was the handling of the complex stratification of multiple identifiers that have been assigned to the objects over the centuries. Regarding this, one of our goals was to provide a unique and persistent identifier to each entity that is described in the Knowledge Base, relying on existing institutional IDs when possible. The use of knowledge graph standard semantic web technologies allowed us to incorporate institutional IDs into consistent URI formats. Each resource represented in the Knowledge Base was assigned a URI which incorporates provenance, type and unique identification.

Another important issue that we faced in the data aggregation was the management of the copyright of the datasets. While the historical data is in the public domain, the contemporary data is owned by the partner institutions, which have different approaches, perspectives and needs regarding copyright. Standard semantic web approaches including knowledge graph development and name spacing, allowed us to maintain a nuanced distinction across dataset licenses. When aggregating the data into a single Knowledge Base, it is necessary to strike a balance between the requirements set by the different institutions, striving to publish as open data whenever possible, but also supporting multiple licensing regimes when publishing the data. Our goal was to balance open data publication with the need to respect different licensing regimes.

Data Mobilisation, Cleaning and Enrichment

This concerned all those tasks that are necessary for producing machine actionable data from previously unstructured textual resources, their modelling and alignment to the Sloane Lab data model and their enrichment with semantic definitions and potential linking to Linked Data.

Sloane's personal annotated copy of John Ray's three-volume work *Historia Plantarum* at the NHM was identified and prioritised as a dataset for mobilisation due to its uniqueness as a taxonomic index to the Sloane Herbarium, the largest surviving part of Sloane's collection. Sloane's copy of Ray's *Historia Plantarum* book is unique in the sense that it holds access to Sloane herbarium specimens by connecting polynomial plant names to locations in the herbarium (Hortus sicci and pages). The resource contains an extremely rich and complex set of data that combine printed material (i.e., plant names) and hand-written marginalia (i.e., volume and page references to the herbarium). Overall, the mobilisation task addressed approximately 3,000 pages, containing approximately 8,500 plant names and 6,400 marginalia referencing 29,600 specimens in the herbarium, together with an additional 2,100 header and footer segments containing a further 4,500 handwritten plant names referencing 10,300 specimens.

Various workflows were implemented to mobilise the data types contained in the three volumes of the *Historia Plantarum*. The printed text of polynomial plant names was OCRed and post processed. Word level and character level error rates were calculated to inform the post-processing phase which involved automatic spellchecking based on specialised domain vocabulary. Plant name entries often include multiple synonyms and further processing and semantic enrichment was conducted for producing finer structures of plant name entries. In addition to the automatic OCR driven method, the data mobilisation task involved manual transcription of marginalia. Human involvement was critical to this task due to limited capacity of automated methods to rectify erroneously detected numbers. Further manual transcription tasks included the transcription of header and footer segments from the *Historia Plantarum*. Such segments contain hand-

written polynomial plant names that complement the list of printed plant names and like marginalia they also contain references to herbarium volume and pages of specimens. The complexity of such hand-written segments in terms of layout and reference numbers do not lend to automated methods.

A further data validation step involved the comparison of the data mobilised from Ray with an inventory of the Sloane Herbarium generated during the project. This provided a mechanism for identifying and correcting transcription errors in the references to specimens mobilised from Ray's *Historia Plantarum*. It also allowed any discrepancies between Sloane's referencing of specimens and the current system for referencing specimens to be identified, thus ensuring that historical and contemporary catalogue records could be linked.

The potential of HTR models for automatic transcription of additional manuscript catalogues was tested by comparing generic Transkribus HTR models and AWS Textract. Sloane's catalogue of Miscellanies served as a testbed as its characteristics (i.e., layout, script, and annotations) are representative for the whole collection of catalogues. The test results were compared with the outcomes of an earlier bespoke HTR model for Sloane's hand. Through the successful working out of such workflows, the team could unlock a wealth of botanical data. Across the three volumes of the NHMs Ray's *Historia Plantarum*, the NHM team in direct collaboration with the UCL technical team digitised data relating to 39,620 plant specimens in Sloane's Herbarium. For each, we provided the pre-Linnean polynomial name used by Sloane, the bibliographic reference for the name and common name (where these are given).

Participatory Engagement

Sloane Lab did not view the computational research of collections as separate from public engagement and impact. Accordingly, this strand of the project asked questions of the interface between collections as data, co-design and public engagement: how can we involve members of the public, researchers, curators and heritage organisations in the machine-actionable contextualisation of individual objects and collections, enabling community-sourced knowledge to enhance and even challenge existing Western-derived descriptions and conceptions?

In answering such questions, we aimed to unify historical and present-day collections and records across taxonomy, geography, context, and audience in a way that accommodates the interests of publics, expert communities, and information organisations. Accordingly, diverse communities (academic, heritage professionals, interested communities and those from non-hegemonic communities) were engaged in the design of the emergent Sloane Lab, exploring with them what questions (and crucially what type of questions) they might wish to ask of a digital national collection and to what extent the Lab could be developed and modified to support the widest possible engagement with collections and collections data and to answer the questions that diverse audiences might have.

The participatory design process developed activities that were linked to the technical team's Sloane Lab Query Service and Knowledge Base tasks; the Sloane Lab data model; the Sloane Lab Data Atlas; and the Sloane Lab API and web application. This participatory design process was a complex, iterative, and innovative one involving a reflective and circular design, moving from participatory engagements into discussions with the technical design and collections teams about the implications for the technical elaboration of the Sloane Lab infrastructure and information modelling and then back again to participatory groups. Building upon the detailed preparation and consultation with the Collections and Technical work

packages in 2022, which led to the development of an agreed participatory plan for a range of co-creation activities with specialist, grassroots organisations, and non-hegemonic communities and the organisation of a pilot exercise of participatory activities with Sloane Lab team members, the participatory team's programme of activities commenced in the last quarter of 2022.

Co-Design Workshops

Between 2022 and 2024 the participatory team, led by the Participatory Consultant (Dr Alda Terracciano) organised eight co-design workshops, in addition to one-to-one sessions, testing sessions, use cases focus groups, and demo UX sessions with individuals and communities. The eight co-design workshops and in person digital activities delivered in collaboration with members of the three teams between 2022 and 2024 engaged a total of 163 people from various professional and cultural backgrounds. These individuals ranged from Sloane scholars, museum professionals, botanists, computer and information scientists to members of the British-Caribbean community with an interest in historical collections and/or plants, artists, amateur gardeners, students, and African or African Caribbean members of the Decolonising the Archive network from a variety of backgrounds. The events included:

- Natural History Museum Family Event 2022: 'Searching for Jamaican plants in the Sloane Lab'
- MTSR Workshop and Focus Group 2022: 'The Sloane Lab data challenge: engaging with and aggregating our challenging pasts'
- UCL Workshop 2022: 'Connecting Jamaican plants across Sloane Collections'
- Heritage Seed Library Workshop 2023: 'Who holds the data? Connecting cultivated plants to specimens in the Sloane Lab'
- Down County Museum Workshop in Northern Ireland 2023
- Sir Hans Sloane Centre Workshop 2023: 'Sloane Lab interoperability: Exploring Northern Ireland's past and present global connections through Sloane's collections'
- Natural History Museum Family Event 2023: 'Searching for Jamaican plants in the Sloane Lab'
- Decolonising the Archive Workshop 2024: 'Exploring the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base, Participatory workshop in collaboration with Decolonising the Archive'

Planned participatory activities began in October 2022 with a half day digital jam workshop held at the Natural History Museum that attracted 20 participants as part of the NHM Explorers Family Festival, with a particular focus on African Caribbean family history researchers. Entitled 'Searching for Jamaican plants in the Sloane Lab', this workshop's aim was to understand use of plain English vs/specialised terminology for botanical specimens from Sloane's voyage to Jamaica, their cultural meaning and uses of online catalogues. The target group was British-Caribbean people interested in plants. The workshop succeeded in acquiring knowledge on ways in which non-specialist users engage with Sloane's botanical Jamaican collection. The workshop gathered information that can be used to develop a search facility to better accommodate non-academic users and remove barriers created by specialist language in the catalogues, raised awareness of Sloane's collections amongst British-Caribbean people and produced new knowledge that can be added to the NHM online public repository.

On 8 November 2022, the participatory team also designed and produced a focus group and workshop held at UCL for a range of people with expertise in data modelling, metadata and semantics. Organised as part of the MTSR conference and in collaboration with members of the technical team this successful event involved 19 participants. This workshop entitled 'The Sloane Lab data challenge: engaging with & aggregating our

challenging pasts’ explored innovative approaches and technological tools to manage, query, and visualize the data, including the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base and the Sloane Lab Data Atlas.

On 7 December 2022, a participatory workshop was held at UCL with 10 participants entitled ‘Connecting Jamaican plants across Sloane collections’. This identified what expert users might want to do with data from various Sloane’s datasets and explored the interoperability of the Sloane Lab database with external digital collections using a selection of specimen from Sloane’s voyage to Jamaica. This workshop was a collaboration with the NHM collections team and targeted those with varying expertise in botanical specimens and interest in Sloane’s collections.

On 19 April 2023, a workshop, co-produced with representatives from the Heritage Seed Library, was held at UCL in collaboration with 22 participants. Entitled ‘Who holds the data? Connecting cultivated plants to specimens in the Sloane Lab’ the workshop examined Sloane’s collection of ‘Vegetable Substances’ and their contemporary relevance to non-experts. The aim was to understand the relevance of historical catalogues in contemporary society through represented plants cultivated in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, especially in relation to members of the Heritage Seed Library. It also aimed to understand what kind of knowledge non-experienced users might be interested to find/search/use when searching the Sloane’s collections online to understand how NHM could enhance its data and how this could enrich the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base and Data Atlas.

On 9 May 2023, a participatory workshop was organised with our project partners at Down County Museum in Downpatrick with 12 participants. It included representatives of various professional disciplines, including academics, people with prior knowledge about Sloane, local residents in Northern Ireland, cultural heritage practitioners and students. The activity was organised in collaboration with the Down County Museum to explore objects from Sloane’s collections included in the British Museum exhibition, including a carved ivory horn, Sloane’s Natural History of Jamaica, a silk embroidery, and an ink drawing. The Collections team was particularly interested in exploring the following themes: curiosity and creativity; the environment and ecology; health and wellbeing; art and science; legacies of collecting, including absences. By testing these different themes or launch points for investigating the exhibition objects as part of the activity, the British Museum aimed to gain some insight into potential outcomes. These would then inform the framework that partner venues could use for developing their community participation activities as part of the touring exhibition.

On 20 July 2023, a participatory workshop entitled ‘Sloane Lab interoperability: Exploring Northern Ireland’s past and present global connections through Sloane’s collections’ was organised in collaboration with the Sir Hans Sloane Centre and the British Museum. The workshop included 21 participants. Its aim was to understand the relevance of the Sloane Lab project’s activities for the local community in Killyleah, Sloane’s birthplace.

On 8 October 2023, ‘Searching for Jamaican plants in the Sloane Lab’ was organised as part of the NHM Explorers Family Festival: The Nature of the Caribbean Islands for Black History Month. This participatory activity was a digital jam on the use of plain English versus specialised terminology for botanical specimens and their cultural meaning. The activity was designed using a selection of plants included in ‘Specimens from Sloane’s Voyage to Jamaica’ and available in the Sloane Herbarium (<https://data.nhm.ac.uk/dataset/sloane-herbarium>). A total of 30 participants took part in the activity.

On 26 March 2024, the final Sloane Lab participatory workshop was held in collaboration with Decolonising the Archive, entitled ‘Exploring the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base’. The co-design made use of the Knowledge

Base by inviting participants to perform searches on it based on their own personal interests. This was then followed by an activity that asked participants about the layout of content warnings on the interface of the Knowledge Base and the Sloane Lab website. The third activity was a storytelling activity for a live performance that took place at the Decolonising the Archive Symposium on 8 June 2024. The activity involved 19 participants including people of African and African Caribbean descent from various backgrounds including artists and arts facilitators, writers, researchers, engineers and other professionals.

The significant amount of data that has been collected through the participatory events was reviewed and methods that can support a rich engagement with and analysis of this data were studied so that an effective workflow for the analysis of this data was established. These activities were planned in line with the objectives which were stated in the Sloane Lab Case for Support and were evaluated in two reports, one assessing participants' engagement through responses to the evaluation forms, and one assessing participants' data related to technical co-design challenges and solutions. This Evaluation Report evaluated participants' co-design contributions against nine thematic categories, each encapsulating a technical area of enquiry explored by the Sloane Lab participatory team. The evaluation of their contributions is followed by a section including a summary of findings and recommendations emerging from them. These are suggestions to members of the technical team, who then decided which of the various recommendations were possible to explore, based on their technical feasibility and potential for impact. Four key cross-activity recommendations were derived from the data analysis: challenging racist narratives, enhancing access, enhancing interpretation and enhancing the user experience (UX) of the interface.

Two further user design workshops were developed by members of the technical team in collaboration with the participatory team as a means of further understanding the functionality of the interface and search engine. These 'UX Labs' worked with 19 individuals to question some of the technical aspects of the Knowledge Base, including search terms and labels, information seeking and retrieval, challenges faced in using the system, the linked relationships found within the Knowledge Base, the appearance and accessibility of the interface, and any other comments and suggestions. These sessions were designed to gain feedback on the user experience and, as with the other eight co-design workshops, this was reported to the technical team to make the necessary changes to the Knowledge Base.

The findings from these workshops and focus groups were reviewed, analysed and recommendations from this analysis were shared with technical and collections' teams to inform the development of the Lab and the type of questioning it could support. In addition, the participatory work package team designed and produced a survey and expression of interest form which resulted in 195 responses from academic and non-academic experts giving rich detail on their current experience and challenges in searching for and using relevant collections data as well as interest in participating in further co-design participatory Sloane Lab activities.

Community Fellows

Another important aspect of Sloane Lab's approach to participatory working was embodied by the Community Fellows scheme it offered, which saw 11 Community Fellows appointed through an open call. Fellows were given a £7,500 stipend and technical assistance to undertake a creative, research led or practice-based three-month project on the digital national collection using the Sloane Lab. The awarded fellows were:

- Dr Gayle Chong Kwan – Travelling Taxonomies

- Dr Dorothy Kyagaba Sebbowa – Anti-Colonial Annotations of Sloane Jamaican References: Inquires into African Slavery
- Anna Sofia Lippolis – Exploring Polyvocal Knowledge in the Sloane Collections
- Dr Gethin Rees – Mapping Sloane’s Generous Collections
- Hannah Cusworth – Bringing Sloane into Conversation with Blackness: Rest, Resistance and Refusal
- Charmaine Watkiss - Investigating Ancestral Cures: Herbs and Healing Traditions of the Transatlantic Caribbean
- Phillip Olney - “The collection and accurate arrangement of these curiosities”: The Display Strategies of Hans Sloane’s Collection as ‘bifocal data’
- Dr Rosalind White - In the Margins of Early Modern Science: Pioneering Women in Sloane’s ‘Paper Museum’
- Rosemary Grennan - Collections of Collections: Building Common Ownership and Shared Archival Practices
- Joanna Byszuk - Exploring Unknown Colonial Terms with Word Vectors
- Lucille Junkere – Jamaican Fibre Plants

The Sloane Lab project particularly welcomed applications from people of the Global Majority and other groups who are underrepresented in and by the heritage and academic sectors and had the aspiration that at least 50% of the fellowships should be awarded to these applicants. In the event five of the eleven fellowships were taken up by members of Global Majority populations.

National and International Heritage Institution Consultation

In parallel, Sloane Lab sought to better understand barriers that currently exist for heritage organisations in the UK, Europe and Australia to be able to participate in digital infrastructures, using participatory and indeed other approaches. Semi-structured interviews were held with 18 individuals in eight UK collecting and heritage organisations and two international aggregators. The interview questionnaire was derived from a review of the literature and through consultation with members with extended experience of conducting qualitative data collection methods. The questionnaire covered the following thematic areas that are less explored in the literature:

- Rationale for participating in unified collections and infrastructures
- Experience with former collaborations
- Technical capabilities and data interoperability
- Legal aspects
- Anticipated use and benefits of unified collections and infrastructures

We found that, to date, the research focus on digital collection unification has tended to be on adopting specific technological solutions and copyright licensing practices. While these are important areas of inquiry, we found that the question of how to unify collections at scale cannot be reduced to these areas, nor by building new platforms. Instead, collections-holding organisations’ capacity to participate in digital infrastructures is dependent on a complex interplay of resource allocation across the sector and within organisations, divergent traditions and requirements of collection description, and different disciplinary

histories and aims. This resulted in recommendations for funders, policymakers, researchers and practitioners of infrastructure projects (see Humbel et al. 2024).

Outside the UK there is a surge of investment in collection data infrastructures. Examples include the European Commission's development towards the 'Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage' or the Australian Research Data Commons' (ARDC) investments into the Trove aggregation platform. For this reason, we were interested to move beyond the UK context and enable academic exchange, professional networking and consultation. Accordingly, the Sloane Lab co-organised two international events.

From 6-7 September 2023 Humanities Data Science and Methodology (HDSM) TU Darmstadt hosted the Sloane Lab Knowledge Exchange Event (Europe) under the theme 'Connecting, co-designing and engaging with digital collections and infrastructures: challenges and case studies'. The event featured paper presentations exploring semantic web and data-driven methods for connecting and researching digital collections; human-centred, ethical and interdisciplinary approaches to linking past and present collections; creative and knowledge-led engagements with digital collections; and future directions. The symposium was attended by approximately 50 individuals, including from Germany, the Netherlands, Luxemburg, Switzerland, Finland and the UK, opening new international conversations between the Towards a National Collection programme and the international collections as data community.

From 22-23 November 2023 the workshop 'Researching the Future of Museum Collections' took place in Australia. The event was hosted by Deakin University Melbourne and convened by Jason Gibson, Gaye Sculthorpe, Andrea Witcomb, Tiffany Shellam (all Deakin University) and Alistair Paterson (University of Western Australia). Sessions addressed cross-cultural and interdisciplinary methods for collaboration, values and absences in collections, distributed collections and collection documentation and technology. The Sloane Lab gave a panel presentation titled: 'Sloane Lab: Why look back to build future shared collections?' The workshop was attended by approximately 50 researchers, curators, and heritage professionals from across the Australian cultural heritage sector as well as participants from New Zealand and the UK.

Both events concluded with focus group discussions, led by the Sloane Lab, to explore the interests and needs of cultural heritage institutions in collections as data infrastructure projects. The discussions were attended by 10 individuals in Darmstadt and eight in Melbourne, who represented archives, libraries, museums and other collecting organisations. Carrying out these focus group discussions enabled the Sloane Lab to build a picture of the status quo of collections as data in the German speaking region and Australia and to bring the findings into conversation with the UK consultations. Preliminary results were presented at the DH2024 conference in Washington D.C. and a follow up publication is planned. Additional immediate impact of the two international events included networking and professional development of Sloane Lab PDRAs, as represented for instance in Marco Humbel's invitation to speak at the 17:15 Colloquium at the ETH-Library Zurich.

Collections Research

The Collections working group mobilised collection data and led on exhibition research (including participatory work with museum communities for the touring exhibition).

Data Mobilisation

In parallel with work on Sloane's copy of Ray's *Historia Plantarum*, the NHM team also generated a new dataset that describes Sloane's collection of *Vegetables and Vegetable Substances* in their entirety. The published dataset (<https://data.nhm.ac.uk/dataset/sloane-vegetable-substances>) provides a complete transcription of the three-volume catalogue to the collection, comprising 12,750 entries and this has been linked to a database of the 8,811 surviving objects. Where images of specimens are available, these have also been integrated into the dataset, with 552 images uploaded to date. Preparatory work was also undertaken to integrate the transcription, together with images of the catalogue pages in the NHM's archive viewer so that the original catalogue and the transcription of it can be viewed simultaneously. This has now been completed:

https://nhm.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/permalink/44NHM_INST/16ehpmm/alma9936352402081

Data enhancement work was also undertaken. The use of abbreviations and terms such as 'the same' or 'Ejusdem' meant that a search across the catalogue for all entries associated with specific people or places is challenging. To address this, provenance data relating to all catalogue entries were captured and standardised facilitating searches by people, specific places, countries and regions. In total, 4,923 catalogue entries (39%) have named individuals associated with them and 4,614 entries (36%) have place data.

The folio-level inventory of the Sloane Herbarium (<https://data.nhm.ac.uk/dataset/sloane-herbarium-inventory>) provides a high-level description of the contents of each of the 37,852 folios contained in the Sloane Herbarium that collectively contain 121,505 plant specimens. A placement for AHRC LAHP student Brad Scott allowed folio-level data on the people and places recorded in Dandy (1958) *The Sloane Herbarium* to be integrated into this herbarium inventory dataset. As a result of this work, 4,847 folios have people associated with them (13%) while 4,211 (11%) had place data, the limited occurrence of these data reflecting the patchiness of provenance data associated directly with folios.

People and place data in the herbarium were standardized with the *Vegetable Substances* data, allowing ease of searching for people and places across the entirety of Sloane's botanical collections and facilitating integration into the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base. As noted above, the inventory data also provided a dataset with which to validate the data extracted from Ray's *Historia Plantarum*. Cross-referencing of these two datasets has, furthermore, ensured that they are comparable and can be integrated.

At the British Museum, data was mobilised for four historical manuscript catalogues and work was undertaken to prepare modern digital collection records for aggregation into the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base. Preparatory to acquiring the datasets from the British Museum modern catalogue, the relevant records had to be researched and revised to put them in a consistent format. This involved research on historical departmental registering systems and aligning them with Sloane's historical catalogue numbering systems so that the Knowledge Base could link the modern and historical catalogue entries. This also involved ensuring that modern records of people and place names were recognisable and linked to the historical entries. Modern catalogue entries were updated with new information produced by this research on biographies of collections and in several instances provided previously unknown origins for objects in the collection, including the identification of a strap from the Gold Coast that had previously been thought to be from the West Coast of North America.

Four further Sloane manuscript catalogues in the British Museum archives (*Intaglios, Cameos & Rings* and *Amuleta Mahumetica*) were imaged and then transcribed by an external service and then double checked

against the originals and marked up with XML to be incorporated into the Knowledge Base. The format of the catalogues was different from previous historical Sloane catalogues that had been transcribed and required new formats for marking up. This process occurred after a major theft at the British Museum of antique gems, several from Sloane's collections, and the process of checking the transcriptions was of assistance in identifying some of Sloane's gems.

Addressing historical gaps, silences and absences in the collection was a key aim of the project and the Collection team collaborating with the technical team to undertake work to visualise and investigate how a data-driven approach to 'absent' objects (or objects not digitally linked) could surface and quantify absence. The visualization of objects in the catalogues provided by the Knowledge Base threw up several questions about what was no longer identifiable from Sloane's collections and which types of objects seemed to have survived more than others. The visualization of the pictures dataset from the *Miscellanies* catalogue, for example, enabled the identification of a series of Maria Sybilla Merian and Guillaume Toulouse watercolours now in albums, to have once been framed and hanging on Sloane's walls. Similarly, research in the archives was used to clarify and identify a series of miniatures that had been transferred to the V&A and National Portrait Gallery in the 1930s and 40s. Creating links to their online records led to a clearer visualization and understanding of how Sloane displayed his paintings in his house.

Touring Exhibition

The project funding for the touring exhibition had built in provision for work with UK museum partners and community engagement to engage members of the public with a physical display around the project. The exhibition, led by the British Museum collections team (Dr Alicia Hughes), formed part of the established National Programme of the British Museum touring exhibitions. This programme is designed to best support the partner museum's ambitions and audiences. Therefore, the purpose of this exhibition was not just to provide a public face for the project but also to collaborate with partners and audiences in the development of the exhibition. As participatory work was central to the Sloane Lab project's research and co-design methodology for the digital platform, it was decided that this methodology should be translated into a co-creation approach to the touring exhibition, as a means of more fully integrating the methodology across the project's outputs, testing what the project was doing and enabling open conversations about the history of the collection that could extend outside of the project's reach to a wider public audience.

The touring exhibition, entitled '*For the curious and interested*' travelled to two venues across the UK in 2024: to our project partners in Down County Museum in Northern Ireland and Ceredigion Museum in Aberystwyth, Wales. A third venue – David Livingstone Birthplace Museum in Scotland was originally intended but was not possible to make happen due to other pressures of the partner venue. The touring exhibition was organised through the British Museum's existing national programme in Learning and Partnerships. Down County Museum was always to be the first venue, given the local links to Hans Sloane (who was born in County Down). The other two original venues were chosen through a competitive process involving an open call for partners who were interested in taking a co-creation approach to the development of the exhibition. Museums responded to the open call, submitting expressions of interest that outlined how hosting and co-creating their version of the exhibition would align with their organisation's collection and audiences and what communities they were interested in working with. From its conception, the exhibition was always intended to be co-created with the partner organisations and groups they wished to work with to co-curate their versions of the exhibition. In this way it supported the participatory research at the heart

of the Sloane Lab project, asking how do people want to connect with the historical collection in the present day? The exhibition title itself – *‘For the curious and interested’* – was taken from Sloane’s original will in which he points to his intended audience for the collection. In paraphrasing it, the exhibition title signalled that it explored what the historical collection means to audiences today.

The exhibition brought together 25 objects from the British Museum, British Library and Natural History Museum, the first time the three institutions had collaborated through exhibition loans in this way. The exhibition sought to physically reconnect these objects from the original connection (as they might be connected in the digital realm) and explore their stories with community groups, project and key external partners, curators and others to shape the content of the show and its interpretation. The exhibition explored the histories of the individual objects and how they were brought together. In particular, it explored Sloane’s legacy with partners and community groups and encouraged challenging conversations around enslavement, empire and colonisation that drove the development of the exhibition and also featured within it. Those challenging conversations fed directly back into the digital work of the project and the legacies we sought to create from Sloane Lab.

The co-curation of the exhibition was led by the partners in each venue, resulting in two different approaches to the collections. At Down County Museum the project successfully worked with the museum partners and a local community group to co-create the exhibition. A specific focus was put on the connections between the collection and the local context in County Down, including Sloane’s family being part of the original settlement of County Down and his acquaintance with the horticulturalist Arthur Rawdon, who also collected plants from Jamaica. Consultation and conversations with the community group resulted in an open dialogue about the history of the collection. The voices of the group members and their responses to the objects were included throughout the exhibition resulting in a conversational tone that engaged visitors in the conversation and debate.

At Ceredigion Museum the exhibition was co-created with a specially-formed local community group from the Global Majority ‘Voices from the Edge’. Ceredigion Museum’s successful funding application to the Association of Independent Museums enabled us to expand the community engagement and the group contributed creative responses, including those that highlighted Sloane’s dependence on the knowledge of enslaved and Indigenous people, but also the life of his wife Elizabeth Langley Rose and the enslaved child he owned in London in 1710.

The touring exhibitions were not seen as a final outcome, rather they formed work across the project and the team’s interpretations of Sloane’s material. For example, learnings from the co-creation process were fed back into the British Museum’s thinking about the way it communicates about Sloane and the Sloane Collections and works with community groups.

Further to this, the touring exhibition has fed directly into the new Sloane Lab display in the British Museum Enlightenment Gallery (Room 1). The content of this new display includes a borrowed work of art created by an artist from the ‘Voices from the Edge’ group that worked with Ceredigion Museum, which brings the story of the enslaved child Sloane owned in London in 1710 to a wider audience. Similarly, Elizabeth Langley Rose, whose inheritance of plantations in Jamaica provided a significant source of wealth for Sloane’s collecting, is more prominently featured (increasing the representation of women within the gallery). A new acquisition by the Museum of a sculptural work created by Sloane Lab Community Fellow Charmaine Watkiss as part of her fellowship (which is also an expansion on a previous collaboration with Dr Alicia Hughes on a British Museum project called ‘Entangled Histories’ in 2022-23) enabled the British Museum to more adequately

engage audiences with the extractive nature of Sloane's botanical collecting and histories of slavery. Following conversations around the language of slavery throughout the project, the British Museum is also updating the interpretation language around the transatlantic trade in enslaved people in Room 1 and across the museum. At the Natural History Museum, work by an AHRC Techne-funded racial justice placement student on the vegetable substances that was supervised by the Natural History Museum team, is contributing towards updating the interpretation of exhibits in the Museum's Hintze Hall.

Research Results

Technical

The project has generated a wealth of research findings that can inform research into the use of digital technologies to build digital collection platforms and applications. We have shown that existing open access Semantic Web standards can go some way towards representing complex, historical and present-day collection records such as that of Sloane. To take one example, in the case of the CIDOC-CRM ontology, to which the Sloane data model is mapped, it was possible to define new classes and properties in a way that is conformant to the requirements of the standard and can be utilised by others.

What the project has also demonstrated, however, is that substantial human labour is nevertheless necessary at crucial points of the digital workflow, from data checking and cleaning to the transcription of fonts or handwriting that still cannot be fully automated by machines. These necessary human interventions are crucial, and digital workflows such as those developed by Sloane Lab, cannot function without them.

Participatory

Sloane Lab has demonstrated that the work of building digital collection infrastructures should not be pursued by a small group of academic and curatorial experts only. It has found that participatory and co-creation approaches to knowledge production (through workshops, exhibitions, fellowship programmes and so on) can result in a new quality of understanding of the kinds of questions that diverse communities wish to ask of digital collections and collection records and museum exhibitions. Project results in relation to this include not only analysis of the information generated through such events but also instruments and guidelines that can inform future approaches to participatory collections as data research and engagement.

Infrastructural

Our main research result is the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base, an interactive portal reuniting the collections of Sir Hans Sloane, which consist of the founding collections of the British Museum, the Natural History Museum and the British Library. The Sloane Lab Knowledge Base enables the cross-searching and investigation of objects, records, people and places in the Sloane Collections. The Sloane Lab Knowledge Base also makes possible the crosslinking of Sloane's historical manuscript catalogue entries with contemporary database records found in museum collections today.

The Sloane Lab Knowledge Base contains 23 datasets (Historical Datasets: *Miscellanea* (seven catalogues); *Fossils I* (six catalogues); *Fossils V* (four catalogues); *Intaglios, Cameos & Rings* (three catalogues); *Amuleta Mahumetica* (one catalogue); *Manuscripts* (one catalogue); *Printed Books* (one catalogue); *Historia Plantarum Vol. 1*; *Historia Plantarum Vol. 2*; *Vegetable Substances*; Contemporary Datasets; British Museum; British Library Manuscripts; NHM Vegetable Substances); 155,0298 RDF statements; 73,623 information objects; 62,482 physical objects; 7,679 people; 1,509 places; 1,579 Species; and 181 Materials.

In addition to the affordances of the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base to enable the data-driven research of Sloane's collections via simple and advanced search mechanisms, the Knowledge Base has already integrated data-driven visualisations to draw attention to how dynamics of colonialism, imperialism and enslavement

have shaped this collection, for example, through the visualisation and aggregation of mentions of people in the collections (for example, enslaved people, women, individuals and places most mentioned in the historical catalogues).

Legacies of Transatlantic Enslavement, Empire and Colonialism and Digital Cultural Heritage

There has been a long history of study of the Sloane Collection and a desire to digitally reassemble it to support ongoing and future research that has taken on new urgency as the legacies of transatlantic enslavement, empire, and colonialism must be directly addressed by collection-based institutions. The generation of new data and integration of data achieved by Sloane Lab permits new ways of querying the collection and the analysis of the data provides new insights. They include how digital methods may help us to better understand the legacies of transatlantic enslavement, empire, and colonialism, and how they are as present in digital cultural heritage data as in the physical museum itself. For example, work on Sloane's botanical collections has allowed a precise estimate of its scale for the first time (130,308 specimens), revealed the extent and patterns of heterogeneity of the collection and of the data associated with it and demonstrated unequivocally the close correlation between patterns of collecting and trade and colonial endeavours of the period, including the trade in enslaved people.

Discipline-Enriching

The sustained and extensive data mobilisation, cleaning and enrichment that the project has engaged in will enhance numerous disciplines and interdisciplinary research. We here present one paradigmatic example of the many that could be rehearsed.

Above, the projects extensive and sustained engagement with botanical data (*Ray's Historia Plantarum*; plant specimens in Sloane's *Herbarium*; Sloane's *Vegetable Substances*) is outlined. The result of this work is the publishing of data (in the Knowledge Base and on the corresponding Natural History Museum repository) that permit, for the first time, digital access to the taxonomic index of Sloane's *Herbarium*, allowing anyone to undertake a taxonomic search using Sloane's taxonomy. Furthermore, the data raises questions relating to Sloane and his collections management practices: for example, which parts of the collection were catalogued in this way and which were not – and why?

Collections

The project has had clear implications for the future work of the British Museum, Natural History Museum and other partners as they develop their own long-term strategies for their digital collections.

Participation in the Sloane Lab project has allowed the British Museum and Natural History Museum colleagues to meet colleagues working on other Discovery Projects. This directly led to important discussions about the similarities and differences that other institutions have faced in working with their digital collections as part of Towards a National Collection projects, and to shared learnings about common approaches to issues such as terminologies, metadata, rights and licensing. For the British Museum and other Independent Research Organisations (IRO) involved in different Discovery Projects there have been key learnings about how to run, manage and support projects at this scale. Discovery Projects are both large

in terms of funding and complex in the work they all do, and partners involved. For the British Museum and other IROs – and HEIs – working on projects of this scale and complexity is unusual. There are important learnings about how IROs need to set up and manage projects of this scale, including the need to distinguish between time needed for someone in the IRO to oversee and act as project wrangler in the institution and time needed for IRO staff to fully participate in the active research.

For the British Museum and Natural History Museum, the project has enabled new work on one of the founding collections of the British Museum (and de facto founding collection of the Natural History Museum) to be continued, and on a scale otherwise not possible without Towards a National Collection. The generation of new data and integration of data permits new ways of querying the collection and the analysis of the data provides new insights. For example, work on Sloane's botanical collections has allowed a precise estimate of its scale for the first time (130,308 specimens); revealed the extent and patterns of heterogeneity of the collection and of the data associated with it and demonstrated unequivocally the close correlation between patterns of collecting and trade and colonial endeavours of the period, including the trade in enslaved people. The data also raises new research questions such as why there is so much variation in the extent of provenance data recorded, why is there so little overlap between individuals who contributed to different sub-collections (such as the *Herbarium* and *Vegetable Substances*) and to which extent can we even consider a 'specimen' in Sloane's botanical collection comparable with modern botanical specimens?

There had been a long history of collaborative research with the British Library and Natural History Museum around Sloane's collections. This included a need to digitally unite the original collection. This had previously been hampered by lack of funding for a digital collections project at the scale needed to make a significant difference. Towards a National Collection has provided the opportunity for the first time to undertake the digital collections research with the right HEI partner needed to drive this project forward. Sloane Lab has made important contributions to reassessing Sloane's collection and how it was created. Genuine new knowledge and understandings have come from directly linking collections through the project.

Key learnings for the British Museum, Natural History Museum and British Library from this project will shape the future work needed to bring together not just the Sloane collection, but our wider shared early collections. The project both shows what is possible using this approach, but also the scale of the practical work needed to tidy digital collections and create a knowledge map to link collections. For the British Museum, a key learning from this is understanding how targeted future digitisation of selected parts of the archive or more detailed work on key parts of the digital object catalogue, plus careful use of AI tools to augment existing information in digital records, could be transformative for addressing key questions without huge amounts of time or money. That the Towards a National Collection programme coincided with the work to recover objects due to the theft from the collection announced in 2023, the commitment to UK Parliament to complete the registration of the collection by 2029 and the priority to work on the Museum archive, has meant Sloane Lab and wider learnings from Towards a National Collection have fed into decisions the museum has made about digital collections.

Sloane Lab has also supported the British Museum's ongoing work and engagement with Australian museums and collections. For the past 15 years the British Museum has had a major focus on understanding the Australian Aboriginal and Torres Strait Island collections at the museum and across other UK collections. This has led to a series of Australian Research Council funded projects with the British Museum as partner of Australian universities and museums. Much of this work has explored the need and limitations of bringing digital collections data together across organisations in the UK, Australia and wider afield. It was for this

reason, that the British Museum partnership with the Collecting the West project (led by Andrea Whitcomb – Deakin University and Alistair Patterson – University of Western Australia) was always seen as part of Sloane Lab. Collecting the West sought to write a history of collections from and in Western Australia – bridging different organisations and types of collections. Collecting the West tried to create aggregated digital collections with limited success.

The discussions with Collecting the West supported by Sloane Lab helped continue and deepen the British Museums’ links with key Australian partners. It also led to Towards a National Collection being able to inform and inspire developments in Australia to bring together different digital collections. Collecting the West, over the course of Towards a National Collection, developed a strong interest in exploring equivalent programmes in Australia. To support this, what was originally seen as a visit by Sloane Lab for discussions with Australian partners, became a central part of a three-day meeting at Deakin University that brought together key people from across Australia and New Zealand to explore the potential for a major centre of excellence bid for collections research. Sloane Lab provided a key presentation on how to link collections, a presentation that brought together post-docs from across the different parts of the project to work together on a common presentation. It also provided the opportunity for Rebecca Bailey to present the Towards a National Collection programme. For the British Museum, this was an important moment in our relationships with Australian institutions that could draw on the previous 15 years’ investment.

Project Outputs

The main output of the project is the digital platform, the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base, a rich interconnected knowledge graph structure, including natural history and pharmaceutical specimens, books, manuscripts, prints, drawings, coins and other objects from across the world:

<https://knowledgebase.sloanelab.org/resource/Start>.

The digital platform aggregates enriched and, in some cases, newly digitised datasets, available through the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base and through the repositories of respective institutions (via the Sloane Lab platform, data is also published as Linked Data, via a SPARQL end point). It includes:

- *Miscellanea* (seven catalogues)
- *Fossils I* (six catalogues)
- *Fossils V* (four catalogues)
- *Intaglios, Cameos & Rings* (three catalogues)
- *Amuleta Mahumetica* (one catalogue)
- *Manuscripts* (one catalogue)
- *Printed Books* (one catalogue)
- *Historia Plantarum* Vol. 1
- *Historia Plantarum* Vol. 2
- *Vegetable Substances* (one catalogue in three volumes)
- Contemporary Datasets
- British Museum
- British Library *Manuscripts*;
- Natural History Museum *Vegetable Substances*
- Folio-level inventory of the Sloane Herbarium

The Sloane Lab Knowledge Base is accessed via the project's central hub sloanelab.org which is an up-to-date resource, featuring all the project's dissemination and public engagement activities. This includes all of the project's participatory workshops and events, which are organised within the top-level menu item 'Participatory Co-Design & Research'. Material from the technical team and other activities are organised by format and author(s), accessible through the 'Sloane Lab Framework'. All activity can be browsed through 'News & Updates', which is an up-to-date feed of all the project's public-facing activities. 'Resources & Publications' provides direct links to project-specific resources, e.g., YouTube and video recordings, as well as to other external resources. Newsletters issued by the project are also accessible.

An important research outcome of the project are the methodologies and instruments that the project has devised not only for the technical aspects of pursuing collections as data research but also for working with diverse communities. Accordingly, the project has closely documented its code and workflows for use by others on the Sloane Lab Git Hub: <https://github.com/sloanelab-org>.

Public Engagement

The main physical outputs of the project included a British Museum National Programmes touring exhibition at two UK partner museums and a new permanent case display in the Enlightenment Gallery at the British Museum. This format best conveyed the work of the project and the stories about objects that can only be told because of bringing the collection together again. Developed in collaboration with partner museums and their communities, it also showcased the participatory work of the Sloane Lab project by conveying the voices, interests and responses that such groups had while working with the Sloane collection. This approach fed into the changes made to the permanent display around Hans Sloane, empire, slavery and colonialism in the Enlightenment Gallery, providing a permanent physical legacy for the Sloane Lab project in an institution visited by over six million people a year.

Sloane Lab Fellows were invited to present their work at the Sloane Lab and Humanities Data Science & Methodology Darmstadt Seminar Series 2024: Critical and creative engagement with historical data.

Recorded sessions are available through the Sloane Lab YouTube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/@SloaneLab/featured>.

Publications

The project has published a number of papers in international, peer-reviewed journals and conference publications:

- At press. Scott, B., Pickering, V., Coulton, R., Nyhan, J., Carine, M. Collecting and Cataloguing the World: The Botanical Collections of Hans Sloane (1660–1753). *Systematics and Biodiversity*
- 2024. Humbel, M., Nyhan, J., Pearlman, N., Vlachidis, A., Hill, JD, Flinn, A. Socio-Cultural Challenges in Collections Digital Infrastructures. *Journal of Documentation*.
- 2024. Terracciano, A., Flinn, A., Nyhan, J. Participation and Inclusion with Digital National Collections: Co-designing the Sloane Lab. *Mimesis Journal* 13:2 (DRHA).
- 2024. Valeonti, F., Vlachidis, A., Nyhan, J., Bikakis, A., Kotarski, R., Jovanovic., P. Decentralising Digital Humanities: Exploring Blockchain Technology and ‘web3’ for the Sloane Lab and Towards a National Collection (TaNC). *Journal of Documentation*.
- 2024. Pickering, V. Mobilising Historical Botanical Data as Research. *Nuncius* 39 (3), 759-774.
- 2023. Humbel, M., Valeonti, F., Metilli, D., Sadek, J., Terracciano, A., Pickering, V., Hughes, A., et al. Looking Back to Build Future Shared Collections: Reports from the Sloane Lab. *Proceedings of the Digital Humanities 2023: Collaboration as Opportunity*. Graz: Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (ADHO), 452–55. <https://zenodo.org/record/8210808>.
- 2024. Humbel, M., Pearlman, N., Hill, JD, Flinn, A., Nyhan, J. Towards International Perspectives on Collection Data Infrastructure Development. *DH2024*. Washington, DC. *Digital Humanities 2024: Book of Abstracts*. VA 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13761079
- 2024. Metilli, D., Hughes, A., Vlachidis, A., Nyhan, J. Investigating Absences in Cultural Heritage Collections: A Sloane Lab Case Study. *DH2024* Washington, DC. *Digital Humanities 2024: Book of Abstracts*. VA 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13761079

- 2022. Sloan, K., 'Sloane's Antiquities. Providing a 'Body of History' Through Beads, Bottles, Brasses and Busts'. *Collective Wisdom – Collecting in the Early Modern Academy*, 211-234. <https://doi.org/10.1484/M.TECHNE-EB.5.119385>
- 2024. Sadek, J., Vlachidis, A., Pickering, V., Humbel, M., Nyhan, J. Leveraging OCR and HTR Cloud Services Towards Data Mobilisation of Historical Resources. *International Journal of Digital Humanities*.

Under Peer Review

- Metilli, D., Vlachidis, A., MacDonald, I., Nyhan, J., Lippolis, A.S., Sadek, J., Hughes, A., Li, J., Flinn, A., Terraciano, A. Multivocality in the Collection of Everything: Towards a Sloane Lab Data Model. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*.
- Carine, M. Digitisation and the History of Botanical Collections and Collecting. *Journal of the History of Collections*.

In progress

- Vlachidis, A., MacDonald, I., Valeonti, F., Sloan, K., Nyhan, J. Data Atlas as a Method for Mapping Cultural Heritage Collections.

Media Engagement

PI J. Nyhan interviewed in: 2021. Andrew, J. 'Search for a Digital National Collection'. *Financial Times*, 22 November 2021. <https://www.ft.com/content/1282bb6e-bbde-4449-8efc-42b43335f8f>

Cross Project Collaboration

Collaboration with other Towards a National Collection projects centred around the technical aspects of the project, specifically on ontologies and vocabularies for data modelling. We have benefited from knowledge exchange with the Unpath'd Waters project, who shared their Towards the UNPATH'D Waters Ontology draft report with us, which sets out "a core ontology to which UNPATH data providers will map their individual database schema, thereby ensuring interoperability between diverse resources" (Unpath'd Waters 2021).

Sustainability and Infrastructure

Project management data, like progress reports, communication, schedule, notes, ethics and governance documentation, are being stored in UCL's Microsoft SharePoint and OneDrive for business server, managed by UCL Information Services Division (ISD) and backed-up daily. Our Sloane Lab SharePoint interface was available to all Sloane Lab team members based in UCL, the Natural History Museum and the British Museum. This material will be retained for internal use and will not be release publicly.

The project's infrastructure exists on AWS cloud services. Our current cloud services utilise Lightsail, EC2, Textract, Lambda, Route 53, Cognito, Backup, VPC, Certificate Manager, IAM, Event bridge. Two separate servers have been deployed. The WordPress server that hosts the project's website carries a specification of 512 MB RAM- 1 vCPU, 20 GB SSD. The development server that hosts the Knowledge Base carries the specification 2 GB RAM - 8vCPU - 200 GiB SSD - Operating System: Ubuntu 22.

Long-term data storage will be supported by UCL's Research Data Storage. The UCL Research Data service guarantees the preservation of research data for 10 years or more. The back-up is daily, and the service was used during the lifetime of the project and can be used after. The triple store data of the Knowledge Base is stored in these services, together with any additional research data. In addition, the technology stack of the VM and server configuration is stored as a ready deployable Docker image.

It is also hoped that long-term storage will be supported by the British Museum and Natural History Museum, via their collections management systems, which guarantee preservation without time limit.

Final Recommendations

The work of building digital heritage platforms, infrastructures and resources should be understood as a techno-participatory encounter. This work requires technical expertise and ongoing, participatory research with diverse audiences, project partners, and the wider heritage sector to execute a digital cultural heritage participatory research paradigm and methodology that accommodates a plurality of perspectives and voices and does not limit publics to interacting with the national collection as curators, librarians, archivists, computer scientists and to how others have modelled it in existing platforms.

The experimental nature of the Towards a National Collection programme means that the use of participatory and co-design methodologies can risk becoming extractive in a time limited project such as Sloane Lab, an issue addressed by Towards a National Collection at a late stage in the programme (Rutherford et al. 2024). Within this wider context of the programme structure and funding, ensuring that symbiotic, co-operative and lasting relationships were formed with participants was a key challenge faced by the Sloane Lab team and one that should be a key consideration of future digital heritage funding programmes.

The project Fellowship scheme brought new voices and expertise into the Sloane Lab. Nevertheless, the elaboration, advertising, interviewing and supervisory work entailed in the Fellowship programme for Sloane Lab staff was substantial and largely invisible. Realistic resourcing of such initiatives should be a key consideration of future digital heritage funding programmes.

Digital technology can play a crucial role in delivering automated and augmented ways of bringing together collections in museums, galleries, libraries, and archives, of mending the broken links between the past and present of the UK's founding collection in the catalogues of the British Museum, Natural History Museum, and the British Library. Yet this work necessarily involves a substantial investment of staff time, in otherwise invisible activities like data cleaning, checking and resolution. Due consideration of this is crucial in future digital cultural heritage projects.

Discussions about digital infrastructure development often lay great emphasis on questions and problems that are technical and legal in nature. Important as technical and legal matters are, more latent, yet potent challenges exist too. Though less discussed in the literature, collecting and heritage organisations' capacity to participate in digital infrastructures is dependent on a complex interplay of resource ontology and allocation across the heritage sector and within collecting and heritage organisations, including divergent traditions of collection description and disciplinary idiosyncrasies. Accordingly, we call for better social-cultural and trans-sectoral (collecting and heritage organisations, universities and technological providers) understandings of collection data infrastructure development.

Sloane Lab sought to facilitate richer, more critical understandings of the origins and development of museum collections by devising computational and conceptual approaches to detecting and exposing often-hidden processes like colonialism, empire and slavery that have shaped collections and their classifications. A five-year period of funding would have enabled deeper analysis and research of the huge wealth of data that the project managed to mobilise and ingest into the Knowledge Base in a three year time frame

Sloane Lab has been built on a trans-sectoral and extramural partnership, across universities, museums libraries and a range of communities. It has required a range of expertise, knowledge and interest that goes far beyond what one individual, disciplinary area or institution can possess. Whilst funding delivered by

schemes like Towards a National Collection is crucial to facilitate cross-sector research, the Sloane Lab project came about due to long standing, trans-sectoral partnerships that far preceded Towards a National Collection. If Sloane Lab has shown that people are just as crucial as technology in the work of imagining how digital platforms that can be used, tell new stories about what can be rediscovered, and reimagined, by linking collections, then this should not be understood as extending to the active research process only. Ongoing ways for universities, heritage institutions, interested and expert individuals and communities to maintain their partnerships outside of short-term Towards a National Collection-like programmes and funding schemes are necessary and require support from funders.

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